

DISTRICT-WISE EMPLOYMENT STATUS OF MGNREGA IN ANDHRA PRADESH

Dr. Choppara Balakotaiah,

Associate Professor, Department of H&SS, AU College of Engineering, Andhra University,
Visakhapatnam

Dr. Yadala Anil Kumar,

Lecturer in Economics, Government Junior College, Madhuravada, Visakhapatnam

Abstract:

The Mahatma Gandhi NREGA sponsors a number of programmes to assist rural residents who are below the poverty line in creating wage jobs and productive assets. MGNREGA is a powerful instrument for ensuring inclusive growth in rural India through its impact on social protection, livelihood security and democratic empowerment. In the scheme central and state government share was 75 percent and 25 percent respectively. MGNREGA differentiates itself from earlier welfare schemes by taking a grassroots-driven approach to employment generation. The programs under the act are demand-driven and provide legal provisions for appeal in the case, work is not provided or payments are delayed. Ever since the scheme was implemented, the number of jobs has increased by 240% in the past 10 years. The scheme has been successful in enhancing economic empowerment in rural India and helping overcome the exploitation of labour. The main objective of the paper is to analyse the employment status of MGNREGS district wise in Andhra Pradesh. Out of 26 districts, more than 90 per cent of the households provided employment equal to 150 days in Alluri Sitarama Raju and Parvatipuram Manyam districts. MGNREGA attempt government of India to tackle the unemployment problem. An employment reduces the poverty.

Index Terms: Rural, Employment, NREGA, Migration, Livelihood Security, Poverty, Households,

Introduction

The unique character of the Act lies in the remarkable opportunities it opens up to transform the development scenario in India. There is a provision for social audit by the local people on the works under taken under the NREGS. Perhaps for the first time transparency and accountability could be seen in a Government Programme. This is the direct outcome of social audits, the conduct of which has been mandated not only in the Right to Information (RTI) Act, but also in the NREGA itself. MGNREGS has been made into an Act by Parliament in 2005 and implemented in a big way in the whole of the country since February, 2006. In its sixth year of existence it is felt that there should be stock taking about the performance of the MGNREGS and its outcome, at least in a sample way and come out with suggestions and approvals of the way it is implemented. Over five years have elapsed since

the inception of the MGNREGS programme. It is now imperative to make an assessment of the MGNREGS from all its important perspectives.

There are several differences between the MGNREGA and other public employment programs. The most fundamental feature of the MGNREGA is the demand driven and rights-based approach above mentioned; the terms and conditions of employment are unique too as it is required that an unemployment allowance has to be paid if work is not provided within 15 days. Workers are further protected as they must be given compensation if wages are not paid within 15 days of work completion. Furthermore, the program looks at the durability of the assets created by the workers as they are intended to provide durable infrastructure in rural areas to ameliorate the livelihood of rural dwellers. The program has a focus on the management of natural resources and 65% of the MGNREGA funds must be spent on water related projects in order to decrease the occurrences of shocks such as droughts, floods and cyclones.

MGNREGA has played a significant role in providing social security to rural households. The scheme provides employment opportunities to rural workers for a minimum of 100 days in a year. This has helped in providing a reliable source of income to rural households, which has improved their living standards. The scheme also provides a guarantee of wages to workers, which has helped in reducing the incidence of wage discrimination and exploitation. MGNREGA also provides several social security measures to rural workers. The scheme provides insurance coverage to workers, which includes medical and accident insurance. This has helped in providing healthcare facilities to rural workers and their families. The scheme also provides maternity benefits to pregnant women, which includes financial assistance for healthcare and nutrition.

In a rural agrarian economy, which is also labour surplus, the population depends on the wages they earn through unskilled casual manual labour. They are vulnerable to the possibility of sinking from transient to chronic poverty in the event of inadequate labour demand or in the face of unpredictable crisis like ill health and disaster. In a context of poverty and un-employment work for programme have been important interventions in developed as well as developing countries for many years. This programme typically provides unskilled manual workers with short term employment on public work such as irrigation, infrastructure, forestation, soil conservation and road construction. The rationale for work for programme provides incomes transfer to poor households during critical times and therefore enable consumption smoothening specially during slack agriculture seasons. In countries with high unemployment rate transfer benefit from work for programmer can prevent poverty worsening especially during lean these programmes may create have the potential to generate a second round of employment benefit as necessary infrastructure is developed. Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (MGNREGA) is one of the most important acts for India's rural poor, the act provides a Legal guarantee for at least 100 days of employment to begin with on asset Creating public works programmes every year at minimum wages to at least one able-bodied person in rural poor and lower middle class house hold. NREGA came into force on sept 7th 2005 and its implementation was notified in phased manner.

Objectives

- ❖ To analyse district wise employment pattern of Households employed under MGNREGS in Andhra Pradesh
- ❖ To examine the district wise and year wise Households Worked under MGNREGS in Andhra Pradesh

The present paper used the secondary data published in MGNREGS official website during 2024-2025, Government of Andhra Pradesh. The data represents like, number of households employed in MGNREGS.

Review of Literature

Suresh Kumar J and D. Shobana (2024) in their paper opined that originality and value of this study lie in its comprehensive approach, examining multiple facets of social security. By offering evidence-based recommendations, this research contributes to the ongoing dialogue on social welfare, providing a foundation for future policy formulations that prioritize inclusivity, efficiency, and sustainability. Ultimately, this study contributes to the ongoing discourse on social security, providing valuable insights for shaping the trajectory of social welfare programs in India.

Balasubramaniam P et al (2022) paper reveals that it has raised the purchasing capacity of the rural people and this has an accelerating effect on the rural economy. The scheme has a positive impact on the livelihood of wage labourers and it improves the socio-economic status of the unskilled workers and stopped out-migration from the villages.

Sanjoy Singh M, Satish Modi and Raj Maurya (2022) study audits under the law. MGNREGA is a safety value since it provides risk factor measures for each personal injury produced by a worker's accident. As seen by the previous results, MGNREGA is well-planned legislation that has proven to be a powerful tool in the hands of rural low-income families and ensures alternative livelihood choices for tribal poor beneficiaries.

Arup Das (2021) in his paper analyses that average person day of employment per household in Assam was 25.43 percent and the employment generated to SCs and STs are 6.59 and 16.18 percent under MGNREGA respectively during 2013-14. But in the same year, in Dhemaji, MGNREGA has provided average employment is 9.57 person days while employment to SCs and STs are 2.06 person days and 34.90 person days respectively where as the corresponding figures were 21.81, 6.07, 15.16, 1.96, and 34.48 respectively in 2014-15.

Eswarappa Kasi (2011) the consequences of developmental programmes often appear to be out of focus and seen at the ground level, there seems to be a gap between what is intended and what is actualized. His paper presents a case study of the social, cultural and economic correlates of the development processes in Addakulapalle, a settlement of Sugali Tribe people, once a semi-nomadic tribe, in Anantapur District of Andhra Pradesh, South India.

Sainath.P (2009) in his article said that a positive step taken by the Rural Development Ministry now allows small but vital assets like farm ponds to be created on the lands of farmers through the MGNREGS. A pond on every farm should be the objective of every government. Incidentally, this would help hugely with the Rabi season. It would also ease the hostility of quite a few farmers towards the MGNREGS. A massive expansion of the MGNREGS will also help cushion the lakhs of laborers struggling to find work and devastated by rising food costs.

Lalit Mathur (2007) revealed in his paper related to the Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (MGNREGA) in its second year. MGNREGA is the first tangible commitment by any government to the poor that they can expect to earn a living wage, without loss of dignity and demand this as a right. The MGNREGA will be extended to the entire country from 2008-09.

Yamini Aiyar and Salimah Samji (2006) in their article suggested how to improve the effectiveness of MGNREGS in rural areas. The earlier employment programmes failed due to the common problems of ineffective targeting, leakages and poor quality asset creation, lack of accountability etc., Hence while developing rules and guidelines for implementation of the MGNREGS more attention should be paid to the lessons that were learnt from past experiences.

Households Employed under MGNREGS in Andhra Pradesh

The Government of Andhra Pradesh has provided employment to 4576998 households from the inception of the programme, and 2668626 households were provided below 50 days of employment followed by 51-99 days of employment completed 1599634 households, equal to 100 days of employment completed 247665 households, 101-149 days of employment 54131 households and only 6942 households completed work days of employment equal to 150 days. The district wise households employed under MGNREGs between 1-50 days in 2024-25 had a lion's share in Prakasam district 187915 (7.04) followed by Vizianagaram 163845 (6.14), Srikakulam 158318 (5.93), Eluru 155945 (5.84) and Kurnool 147358 (5.52) whereas the lowest employment provided districts like., Visakhapatnam 14434 (0.54 %) next in order Guntur 49986 (1.87%), East Godavari 54279 (2.03%), Parvathipuram Manyam 65355 (2.45%) and Annamayya 73431 (2.75%). Srikakulam district highest number of households provided employment between 51-99 days reported at 144510 (9.03%) and the lowest one recorded at 10428 (0.65%) in Visakhapatnam. 100 days employment provided households higher in Tirupati 25284 (10.21) and Srikakulam 24833 (10.03%) and the lowest districts Guntur 843 (0.34%) and Visakhapatnam 2314 (0.93%). Between 101-149 days of employment provided households is highest in Alluri Sitharama Raju district 35290 (65.19%) next in order Parvathipuram Manyam 13799 (25.49%) these two district also shows highest position provided employment equal to 150 Days. Out of 26 districts, more than 90 per cent of the households getting employment equal to 150 days in these two districts. This indicated that these two districts represents a major proportion of population belong to Schedule Tribes (See Table-1).

Table-1
District-wise Employment Provided (Households Employed) under MGNREGS: 2024-2025

District	1-50 Days		51 - 99 Days		Equal to 100 Days		101 - 149 Days		Equal to 150 Days	
	HHs	%	HHs	%	HHs	%	HHs	%	HHs	%
Alluri Sitharama Raju	75980	2.85	83046	5.19	16921	6.83	35290	65.19	4348	62.63
Anakapalli	102732	3.85	89071	5.57	14240	5.75	450	0.83	15	0.22
Anantapur	117615	4.41	73936	4.62	13334	5.38	17	0.03	0	0.00
Annamayya	73431	2.75	64425	4.03	10689	4.32	38	0.07	0	0.00
Bapatla	126460	4.74	39644	2.48	3473	1.40	0	0.00	0	0.00
Chittoor	77812	2.92	60400	3.78	10359	4.18	26	0.05	1	0.01
East Godavari	54279	2.03	36363	2.27	7302	2.95	0	0.00	0	0.00
Eluru	155945	5.84	80760	5.05	11593	4.68	451	0.83	115	1.66
Guntur	49986	1.87	15250	0.95	843	0.34	0	0.00	0	0.00
Kakinada	105840	3.97	47837	2.99	5429	2.19	102	0.19	3	0.04
Konaseema	79755	2.99	34428	2.15	8578	3.46	0	0.00	0	0.00
Krishna	87646	3.28	46924	2.93	9891	3.99	0	0.00	0	0.00
Kurnool	147358	5.52	52383	3.27	5909	2.39	18	0.03	0	0.00
Nandyal	115732	4.34	43439	2.72	5029	2.03	69	0.13	8	0.12
Nellore	140769	5.27	70071	4.38	4014	1.62	1	0.00	0	0.00
NTR	84785	3.18	53840	3.37	8075	3.26	83	0.15	9	0.13
Palnadu	146501	5.49	43617	2.73	5295	2.14	101	0.19	11	0.16
Parvathipuram Manyam	65355	2.45	82071	5.13	15114	6.10	13799	25.49	1995	28.74
Prakasam	187915	7.04	95690	5.98	5264	2.13	119	0.22	9	0.13
Sri Sathya Sai	88589	3.32	67619	4.23	13081	5.28	0	0.00	0	0.00
Srikakulam	158318	5.93	144510	9.03	24833	10.03	3401	6.28	424	6.11
Tirupati	85563	3.21	58294	3.64	25284	10.21	30	0.06	3	0.04
Visakhapatnam	14434	0.54	10428	0.65	2314	0.93	0	0.00	0	0.00
Vizianagaram	163845	6.14	131938	8.25	11979	4.84	134	0.25	1	0.01
West Godavari	76928	2.88	20028	1.25	2350	0.95	0	0.00	0	0.00
Y.S.R	85053	3.19	53622	3.35	6472	2.61	2	0.00	0	0.00
Andhra Pradesh	2668626	100.00	1599634	100.00	247665	100.00	54131	100.00	6942	100.00

Source: MGNREGA Official Web site, Government of Andhra Pradesh

The Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (MGNREGA) aims to enhance livelihood security in rural areas by providing at least 100 days of guaranteed wage employment in every financial year to every household whose adult members volunteer to do unskilled manual work. Table 2 presents District wise Total Households Worked in MGNREGS: 2020-21 to 2024-25 in Andhra Pradesh. In the Year 2024-25 majority of Households worked in Srikakulam district with 3.32 lakhs occupied top place, next in order to Vizianagaram 3.08 lakhs, Prakasam 2.9 lakhs, Eluru 2.5 lakhs and Nellore 2.16 lakhs in Andhra Pradesh. Prakasam district takes top place with 4.85 lakhs

Households Worked in MGNREGS in the year 2020-21, followed by Srikakulam 4.37 lakhs, East Godavari 4.28 lakhs, Anantapur 4.22 lakhs and Vizianagaram 4.1 lakhs in Andhra Pradesh.

Table -2**District wise Total Households Worked [In Lakhs] in MGNREGS: 2020-21 to 2024-25**

District	2024-25		2023-24		2022-23		2021-22		2020-21	
	No.	%								
ALLURI SITHARAMA RAJU	2.12	4.62	2.05	4.40	1.96	4.28	0	0.00	0	0.00
ANAKAPALLI	2.07	4.51	2.07	4.45	2	4.36	0	0.00	0	0.00
ANANTAPUR	2.06	4.49	1.99	4.27	2.01	4.39	4.07	8.71	4.22	8.88
ANNAMAYYA	1.49	3.25	1.61	3.46	1.49	3.25	0	0.00	0	0.00
BAPATLA	1.7	3.71	1.7	3.65	1.68	3.67	0	0.00	0	0.00
CHITTOOR	1.49	3.25	1.49	3.20	1.47	3.21	3.13	6.70	3.24	6.82
EAST GODAVARI	0.98	2.14	1.01	2.17	1.02	2.23	4.15	8.88	4.28	9.01
ELURU	2.5	5.45	2.67	5.74	2.71	5.91	0	0.00	0	0.00
GUNTUR	0.66	1.44	0.73	1.57	0.71	1.55	3.45	7.38	3.39	7.13
KAKINADA	1.6	3.49	1.56	3.35	1.58	3.45	0	0.00	0	0.00
KONASEEMA	1.23	2.68	1.24	2.66	1.25	2.73	0	0.00	0	0.00
KRISHNA	1.45	3.16	1.52	3.27	1.47	3.21	3.23	6.91	2.99	6.29
KURNOOL	2.07	4.51	2.01	4.32	1.93	4.21	3.45	7.38	3.67	7.72
NANDYAL	1.65	3.60	1.65	3.54	1.64	3.58	0	0.00	0	0.00
NELLORE	2.16	4.71	2.24	4.81	2.08	4.54	2.64	5.65	2.59	5.45
NTR	1.47	3.21	1.5	3.22	1.41	3.08	0	0.00	0	0.00
PALNADU	1.97	4.30	1.98	4.25	1.92	4.19	0	0.00	0	0.00
PARVATHIPURAM MANYAM	1.77	3.86	1.76	3.78	1.73	3.77	0	0.00	0	0.00
PRAKASAM	2.9	6.32	3.09	6.64	3.23	7.05	4.65	9.95	4.85	10.21
SRI SATHYA SAI	1.7	3.71	1.49	3.20	1.51	3.29	0	0.00	0	0.00
SRIKAKULAM	3.32	7.24	3.38	7.26	3.31	7.22	4.26	9.11	4.37	9.20
TIRUPATI	1.7	3.71	1.78	3.82	1.79	3.91	0	0.00	0	0.00
VISAKHAPATANAM	0.27	0.59	0.28	0.60	0.27	0.59	3.67	7.85	3.85	8.10
VIZIANAGARAM	3.08	6.72	3.21	6.90	3.12	6.81	4.14	8.86	4.1	8.63
WEST GODAVARI	0.99	2.16	1.04	2.23	1.07	2.33	3.41	7.30	3.43	7.22
Y.S.R	1.46	3.18	1.48	3.18	1.46	3.19	2.48	5.31	2.56	5.39
ANDHRA PRADESH	45.85	100.00	46.55	100.00	45.83	100.00	46.74	100.00	47.52	100.00

Source: MGNREGS Official Website

Conclusion

To sum up, more than 90 per cent of the households employed between 101-150 days under MGNREGS in Alluri Sitharama Raju and Parvathipuram Manyam districts. As mentioned earlier the works under NREGS should be useful to the community and sustainable. This aspect of NREGS has been receiving much criticism from different sections of the society and frequently seen in both print and electronic media. districts with lowest poverty rates have higher efficiency score which indicates efficiency in implementation of the scheme MGNREGS implementation efficiency and poverty indicates negative relationship. Similarly, the literacy level and MGNREGS implementation efficiency indicates that there was positive relationship. Therefore, education and awareness about scheme plays an important role for better implementation of the scheme. The global literature review on MGNREGA suggests that the program has had a positive impact on the livelihoods of rural households in India, with a particular emphasis on women. The program has provided employment opportunities, increased wages, improved agricultural productivity, and reduced poverty. Additionally, MGNREGA has shown to reduce rural-urban migration, child labor, and improve school attendance.

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